

On the quantum super Virasoro algebra

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ABSTRACT

The quantum super-algebra structure on the deformed super Virasoro algebra is investigated. More specifically we established the possibility of defining a non trivial Hopf super-algebra on both one and two-parameters deformed super Virasoro algebras.

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Quantum algebras (quantum groups)[1, 2], are generalizations of the usual Lie algebras to which they reduce for appropriate values of the deformation parameters. From the mathematical point of view they are Hopf algebras [3].

Quantum superalgebras appeared naturally when the quantum inverse scattering method [4] was generalized to the super-systems [4]. Related R-matrix were considered in [5, 6] and simple examples were presented in [7]. The works [8, 9, 10] are devoted to the q-bosonization of the q-superalgebras. The simple example of the dual objects, i.e. quantum supergroups, were investigated in [10, 11, 12]. A complete classification of finite dimensional Lie Superalgebras over C has been give by Kac [13, 14] and Scheurnert [15]. Supersymmetry seems to be in the realm of almost all attempts to obtain a unified theory of all interactions [17, 18]. In particular, many problems of string theory are solved once supersymmetry is introduced [19, 20]. The interplay of supersymmetry and conformal invariance is an interesting application of the rules up to now. The two-dimensional superconformal field theory can be treated from a group theoretical point of view, the basic ingredient is the two-dimensional superconformal algebra, which is infinite dimensional called the super Virasoro , see [21] and references therein, The central extension of the super Virasoro algebra leads to the so called the Ramond-Neveu-Schwarz algebras[22, 23]. A supersymmetric extension of the work of Curtright and Zachos is given in [24] by using a quantum superspace approach [25, 26].

The use of quantum superalgebras in physics became popular with the introduction of the deformed harmonic oscillator as a tool for providing a realization of the quantum (super) algebra [27, 28, 7] . Particularly, a great deal of attention has been paid to the deformation of the Virasoro algebra [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34] and the super Virasoro algebra [35, 36, 24]. Several investigations of the latter super-algebra are based on the coordinates and derivatives on super space [24, 35]. The quantum group structure on the Deformed Virasoro algebra is given in [37, 38] However, the existence of a quantum super-algebra structure of the deformed super Virasoro algebra is still an open question. The purpose of this paper is to give a realization of the deformed super Virasoro algebra in terms of bosonic and fermionic algebra operators and define a quantum super-algebra structure on this deformed super-algebra. In ref. [39], an algebraic deformation (associated to an R-matrix of unit square) which allows to a non trivial Hopf super-algebra structure on the super Virasoro and Ramond-Neveu-Shwarz algebras will be

investigated.

First, let us recall that the classical super Virasoro algebra ($sVir$) is defined as an infinite super-algebra generated by the generators $\{L_n, G_n, F_n; n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ satisfying the defining relations [19, 21]

$$\begin{aligned}
[L_n, L_m] &= (n - m)L_{n+m}, \\
[F_m, G_n] &= G_{n+m}, \\
[L_n, F_m] &= -mF_{n+m}, \\
[F_m, F_n] &= 0, \\
[L_m, G_n] &= (m - n)G_{n+m}, \\
[G_m, G_n] &= 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

and that the Hopf super-algebra structure on the enveloping super-algebra of this classical super-algebra $U(sVir)$ is trivial. The \mathbb{Z}_2 -grading on this super-algebra is defined by requiring that $\deg(L_i) = \deg(F_i) = 0$ and $\deg(G_i) = 1$ for ($i \in \mathbb{Z}$). Further, the bracket $[\cdot, \cdot]$ in (1) stands for a graded one

$$[x, y] = xy - (-1)^{\deg(x)\deg(y)}yx.$$

A possible realization of the classical super Virasoro algebra (1) is given as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
L_k &= -(a_+)^{k+1}a_-, \\
G_n &= (a_+)^{n+1}f_+a_-, \\
F_n &= (a_+)^n f_+f_-
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where the operators $\{a_+, a_-, 1\}$ generate the classical bosonic algebra

$$\begin{aligned}
a_-a_+ - a_+a_- &= 1 \\
[1, a_\pm] &= 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and the remaining ones $\{f_+, f_-, 1\}$ generate the classical fermionic algebra given by

$$\begin{aligned}
f_-f_+ + f_+f_- &= 1 \\
[1, f_\pm] &= 0, \quad (f_\pm)^2 = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

A q -deformed version of the super Virasoro algebra will be defined by the

generators $\{L_n, G_n, K_n; n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ and the following q -deformed relations

$$\begin{aligned}
q^{l-k}L_lL_k - q^{k-1}L_kL_l &= [l-k]L_{k+l} \\
F_mG_n - G_nF_m &= G_{n+m}, \\
L_lF_k - q^{2k}F_kL_l &= -q[[k]]F_{k+l}, \\
q^{n-m}F_mF_n - q^{m-n}F_nF_m &= \lambda[n-m]F_{n+m}, \\
q^{l-k}L_lG_k - q^{k-1}G_kL_l &= [l-k]G_{k+l}, \\
G_mG_n + G_nG_m &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

(where $[x] = \frac{q^x - q^{-x}}{q - q^{-1}}$, $[[x]] = \frac{1 - q^{2x}}{1 - q^2}$ and $\lambda = q - q^{-1}$).

The q -deformed super-algebra (5) can be realized in terms of a q -deformed bosonic algebra generators $\{a_+, a_-, 1\}$ and a classical fermionic algebra generators $\{f_+, f_-, 1\}$ which are such that

$$\begin{aligned}
[a_-, a_+]_{q^2} &= 1, & \{f_-, f_+\} &= 1 \\
[a_{\pm}, f_{\pm}] &= 0, & [a_{\mp}, f_{\pm}] &= 0, \\
(f_-)^2 &= 0, & (f_+)^2 &= 0, \\
[1, a_{\pm}] &= 0, & [1, f_{\pm}] &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

(where $[a, b]_{\alpha} = ab - \alpha ba$).

In fact, the following operators

$$\begin{aligned}
L_k &= -q(a_+)^{k+1}a_-, \\
G_n &= (a_+)^{n+1}f_+a_-, \\
F_n &= (a_+)^n f_+ f_-
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

generate the q -deformed super Virasoro algebra (5).

Now we define the quantum super-algebra structure on the q -deformed enveloping super-algebra of the q -deformed super Virasoro algebra $U_q(sVir_q)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta(L_i) &= L_i \otimes T_i + T_i \otimes L_i, \\
\Delta(G_i) &= G_i \otimes R_i + R_i \otimes G_i, \\
\Delta(F_i) &= F_i \otimes K_i + K_i \otimes F_i, \\
\epsilon(L_i) &= 0, \\
\epsilon(G_i) &= 0, \\
\epsilon(F_i) &= 0, \\
S(L_i) &= -S(T_i)L_iT_i^{-1}, \\
S(G_i) &= -S(R_i)G_iR_i^{-1}, \\
S(F_i) &= -S(K_i)F_iK_i^{-1},
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where the operators $\{K_i, T_i, R_i, \quad i \in Z\}$ are additional invertible even elements of $U_q(sVir_q)$ which reduce to the unity operator when the deformation parameter $q = 1$.

From the consistence of the costructures on q -deformed super Virasoro algebra generators with the basic axioms of the Hopf super-algebra structure (co-associativity, co-unity and antipode), we deduce that the costructures on the additional elements are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta(T_i) &= T_i \otimes T_i, \\
\Delta(R_i) &= R_i \otimes R_i, \\
\Delta(K_i) &= K_i \otimes K_i, \\
\epsilon(T_i) &= 1, \\
\epsilon(R_i) &= 1, \\
\epsilon(K_i) &= 1, \\
S(T_i) &= T_i^{-1}, \\
S(R_i) &= R_i^{-1}, \\
S(K_i) &= K_i^{-1}.
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Further, the consistence of the Hopf super-algebra structure (8) with the deformed commutations relations (5), (i.e. using the fact that the coproduct (Δ) and counit (ϵ) operations must be super-algebra homomorphisms, and that the coinverse (S) must be super-algebra anti-homomorphism) we obtain the following relations between the q -deformed super Virasoro algebra generators and the additional elements.

$$\begin{aligned}
L_k T_l &= q^{2(k+1)l} T_l L_k, \\
L_l K_k &= q^{-1k} K_k L_l, \\
G_k K_l &= K_l G_k, \\
T_l F_k &= q^{(2+1)k} F_k T_l, \\
F_k R_l &= R_l F_k, \\
G_k T_l &= q^{2(1+k)l} T_l G_k, \\
L_l R_k &= q^{2(l+1)k} R_k L_l, \\
F_k K_l &= q^{-2(k+1)l} K_l F_k, \\
G_k R_l &= R_l G_k,
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where the additional generators must satisfy the following relations between

them

$$\begin{aligned}
T_k T_l &= T_l T_k = T_{k+l}, \\
T_k K_l &= K_l T_k = K_{l+k}, \\
R_k K_l &= K_l R_k, \\
K_k K_l &= K_l K_k = K_{l+k}, \\
R_k R_l &= R_l R_k = R_{k+l}, \\
T_l R_k &= R_k T_l = R_{k+l}.
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Considering now the two-parameters (p, q) -deformation version of the super Virasoro algebra given by

$$\begin{aligned}
q^{l-k} L_l L_k - q^{k-1} L_k L_l &= [l-k] L_{k+l}, \\
F_m G_n - G_n F_m &= G_{n+m}, \\
L_l F_k - q^{2k} F_k L_l &= -q[[k]] F_{k+l}, \\
q^{n-m} F_m F_n - q^{m-n} F_n F_m &= \lambda[n-m] F_{n+m}, \\
q^{l-k} L_l G_k - p^{2l} q^{k-1} G_k L_l &= [l-k] G_{k+l}, \\
G_m G_n + G_n G_m &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

which can be realized as

$$\begin{aligned}
L_k &= -q(a_+)^{k+1} a_-, \\
G_n &= p^{-2} (a_+)^{n+1} f_+ a_-, \\
F_n &= (a_+)^n f_+ f_-,
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where the generators $\{a_+, a_-, f_+, f_-, 1\}$ satisfy now

$$\begin{aligned}
[a_-, a_+]_{q^2} &= 1, & \{f_-, f_+\} &= 1 \\
[a_+, f_+]_{p^2} &= 0, & [a_-, f_+]_{p^{-2}} &= 0, \\
[a_-, f_-]_{p^2} &= 0, & [a_+, f_-]_{p^{-2}} &= 0, \\
(f_-)^2 &= 0, & (f_+)^2 &= 0. \\
[1, a_{\pm}] &= 0, & [1, f_{\pm}] &= 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

In this case, the (p, q) -quantum super-algebra structure on the $U_{p,q}(sVir_{p,q})$, will be given by the same costructures on the q -deformed super Virasoro algebra generators (8) and with the same costructures on the additional even generators. But the deformed relations between the (p, q) -deformed super

Virasoro algebra generators and the additional elements are

$$\begin{aligned}
L_k T_l &= q^{2(k+1)l} T_l L_k, \\
L_l K_k &= q^{(1+l)k} K_k L_l, \\
G_k K_l &= K_l G_k, \\
F_k T_l &= q^{(k-1)l} T_l F_k, \\
F_k R_l &= R_l F_k, \\
T_l G_k &= q^{-2(1+k)l} p^{(k+2)l} G_k T_l, \\
L_l R_k &= q^{2(l+l)k} p^{-kl} R_k L_l, \\
F_k K_l &= q^{-2(k+1)l} K_l F_k, \\
G_k R_l &= R_l G_k,
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where the additional generators $\{K_i, T_i, R_i, \quad i \in Z\}$ must satisfy the relations (11) as in the one parameter deformation case and reduce to the unity operator when the deformation parameters p, q reduce to their classical values ($p = q = 1$)

In concluding we report that we established that it is possible to define a non trivial Hopf super-algebra structure on the deformed super Virasoro algebra, if we extend its deformed enveloping super-algebra with a set of additional even invertible elements. A consistence realisation of the additional even invertible elements $\{K_i, T_i, R_i, \quad i \in Z\}$ will be given elswere [40]

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